

Parametric and free-form airgap optimization of an inductor

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This paper addresses the gradient-based design optimization of the airgap profile of an inductor to minimize proximity-effect losses. In particular, parametric and free-form optimizations are conducted based on the shape derivative obtained from the adjoint method. The objective is to minimize the magnetic energy inside the conductors, which is related to the proximity effect and additional AC losses while keeping the inductance value constant. It is shown that the optimized airgap profile is curved in order to concentrate the flux lines away from the (fixed) conductors. The implementation uses the open-source finite-element toolbox NGSolve; all the codes are freely available.

Index Terms—Inductor, AC losses, Parametric optimization, Shape optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

DESIGN optimization is used intensively for the conception of electromagnetic devices. Using gradient-free methods, some work has been done on the design of inductors to limit proximity losses due to the fringing effect by optimizing the conductors [1] or the airgap profile [2]. The best configuration prevents the flux lines from crossing the conductors. Even if gradient-based methods generally converge faster to a (local) optimum, they are less common. A possible explanation is the high CPU cost required to compute the derivative of the objective functions using finite differences. However, appropriate mathematical tools such as the adjoint method make the computation of sensitivities simple and efficient. In particular, the computation of shape derivatives enables parametric and free-form optimization. While shape differentiation is standard in real-valued problems and can even be automatized [3], its application to complex-valued problems is not common and would be of high interest in electrical engineering. In particular, it is not yet fully supported by the NGSolve's `DiffShape` built-in function. This paper provides a concrete application of shape derivative on parametric and free-form optimizations to minimize proximity AC losses in an inductor due to the fringing effect near the air gap. All the Python codes use the NGSolve package and are freely available [\[link to Zenodo\]](#).

II. MATHEMATICAL MODEL

A. Physical equations

We consider the magneto-quasistatic analysis in the frequency domain of a 2D region $\Omega = \Omega_a \cup \Omega_f \cup \Omega_c$, where

- Ω_a is the air region associated with a magnetic permeability $\mu_0 = 4\pi \times 10^{-7}$ H/m;
- Ω_f is the ferromagnetic region associated with a permeability $\mu_f = 1000\mu_0$. The iron losses are neglected;
- Ω_c is the region of electrical conductors. Its complex permeability comes from homogenized models depending on the frequency and wires configuration [4]. The adopted

value is $\underline{\mu}_c = \mu_0 \exp(-i\delta)$ with $\delta = 0.1$ rad, i being the unit imaginary number such that $i^2 = -1$.

The state equation then reads

$$-\nabla \cdot \left(\left(\frac{\chi_a}{\mu_0} + \frac{\chi_f}{\mu_f} + \frac{\chi_c}{\underline{\mu}_c} \right) \nabla \underline{a} \right) = \chi_c j, \quad (1)$$

where \underline{a} is the out-of-the-plane component of the magnetic vector potential phasor such that $\underline{b} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ -1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \nabla \underline{a}$, and j the (real) current density that is the phase reference and assumed to be sinus. The AC losses come from proximity effect in the conductor that is included in the imaginary part of the permeability and reads

$$P(\underline{a}) = s l_z \pi f \int_{\Omega} \text{Im} \left(\frac{\chi_c}{\underline{\mu}_c} \right) |\nabla \underline{a}|^2 dx, \quad (2)$$

while the inductance expresses as

$$L(\underline{a}) = \frac{s l_z}{I^2} \int_{\Omega} \text{Re} \left(\frac{\chi_a}{\mu_0} + \frac{\chi_f}{\mu_f} + \frac{\chi_c}{\underline{\mu}_c} \right) |\nabla \underline{a}|^2 dx, \quad (3)$$

where $s = 4$ is the symmetry coefficient, $l_z = 1$ cm is the z -thickness (fringing is neglected in the z direction), I is the electric current amplitude set to 2 A with 200 turns. The model is discretized and solved using NGSolve¹.

B. Shape derivatives

The aim is to minimize the AC losses (8) while keeping the inductance (9) to a given value $L_0 = 1$ mH. To do so, we allow modifications of the airgap profile only, i.e., the airgap boundaries of Ω_f and Ω_a can move while Ω_c remains unchanged. The initial design is given in Figure 1a.

The sensitivity of the objective and constraint functions with respect to a modification of the airgap profile can be evaluated using shape derivatives [3]. In a nutshell, the shape derivative of a function g is a linear form, that can be tested with any vector field ϕ . In other words, for a small $t > 0$ and a given

¹<https://ngsolve.org/>

Fig. 1: Simulation setup.

transport field $\phi \in (H^1(\Omega))^2$, it is defined by the following limit:

$$dg(\Omega)(\phi) = \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{g(\Omega + t\phi) - g(\Omega)}{t}. \quad (4)$$

The freedom to choose ϕ enables non-parametric optimization; two examples will be given in Section III. Since we assume that the coil region Ω_c remains fixed, we consider only vector fields ϕ which vanish inside Ω_c and whose normal component on $\partial\Omega_c$ vanishes. In this case, the shape derivatives of the AC losses and the inductance read

$$dP(\Omega)(\phi) = \text{Re} \left(\int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{\chi_a}{\mu_0} + \frac{\chi_f}{\mu_f} \right) A_{\phi} \nabla \underline{a} \cdot \nabla (\underline{p}_P)^* dx \right), \quad (5)$$

$$dL(\Omega)(\phi) = \text{Re} \left(\int_{\Omega} \left(\frac{\chi_a}{\mu_0} + \frac{\chi_f}{\mu_f} \right) A_{\phi} \nabla \underline{a} \cdot \left(\frac{\nabla \underline{a}}{I^2} + \nabla \underline{p}_L \right)^* dx \right), \quad (6)$$

respectively, with the real 2×2 matrix $A_{\phi} = \text{div} \phi I_2 - \partial \phi - \partial \phi^{\top}$. Here, the adjoint state \underline{p}_P solves the equation

$$-\nabla \cdot \left(\left(\frac{\chi_a}{\mu_0} + \frac{\chi_f}{\mu_f} + \frac{\chi_c}{\mu_c} \right)^* \nabla \underline{p}_P \right) = -P'(\underline{a}), \quad (7)$$

and \underline{p}_L is defined analogously by replacing the right-hand side by $-L'(\underline{a})$. The detailed calculation will be provided in the extended version of the article.

III. OPTIMIZATION RESULTS

In this section, the results are given for parametric and nonparametric optimizations using an augmented Lagrangian algorithm. A summary is provided in Table I.

A. Parametric optimization

Defining ϕ as the displacement of the airgap border by moving one of the four control points shown in Figure 1b leads to a parametric optimum shown in Figure 2a. The airgap is shaped to carry high flux away from the conductor, which minimizes the losses.

B. Free-form shape optimization

Choosing a parametrization restricts the possible shapes. Setting ϕ such that $\forall \varphi \in (H^1(\Omega))^2$, $\langle \phi, \varphi \rangle = -dg(\Omega)(\varphi)$ with $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle$ an arbitrary scalar product leads to free-form optimization. The resulting descent direction is used to deform the airgap

Fig. 2: Final results of the optimizations.

profile. We use the Mmg library² to ensure an acceptable mesh quality throughout the optimization. The optimized shape is given in Figure 2b.

TABLE I: Optimization results.

Optimization Type	Iterations to Convergence	P (W)	L (mH)
Reference	-	13.16	1.00
Parametric	55	6.43	0.999
Free form	435	3.86	1.00

IV. CONCLUSION

We have conducted gradient-based optimization of an inductor. With or without parametrization, computing the gradient is possible using the shape derivative, whether the problem is parametrized or not. This paper explains the methodology, and automated computation is even possible with NGSolve. In the final paper, more details will be given especially regarding the calculation of the shape derivative using complex numbers.

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²<https://www.mmgtools.org/>